

The Influence of Product Quality and Service Quality on Consumer Satisfaction and Purchasing Decisions

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to see and determine the influence of product satisfaction and service quality on consumer satisfaction and purchasing decisions, both partially and simultaneously. The form of this research is quantitative descriptive research. Data and information collection uses a questionnaire as a research instrument. The population in this research is all consumers who purchased food or beverage products at the Bang Pendi Rantauprapat Cafe in the period June 2023 to August 2023, namely 540 people and the sample was determined using the Slovin formula with a margin of error of 5% so that the total sample was 277 buyers. Data analysis uses Structure Equation Version (SEM) with the help of the SmartPLS version 3 software program. The results of the research show that product quality (X1) has a good and broad influence on consumer satisfaction (Y) with a tcount value of 6.591 > ttable of 1.96 with percentage of 65.9%. Service quality (X2) has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction (Y) with a calculated t value of 2.603 > t table value of 1.96 with a percentage of 26.0%. Product quality (X1) has a good and partially large influence on purchasing choices (Z) with the price t statistic being higher than the t price table, namely 6.377 > 1.96 with a price percentage of 63.7%. Excellent service (X2) has a partially effective and large influence on purchasing decisions (Z) with t calculated being greater than t table, namely 5,168 > 1.96 with a percentage of 51.6%. Product quality (X1) and service quality (X2) simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions (Z) through customer satisfaction (Y) with a t value greater than t table, namely 8.636 > 1.96 with a percentage of 86.30%.

INTRODUCTION

The culinary business in Indonesia is visibly growing and spreading everywhere, showing that the culinary industry seems to continue to develop and is even said to be growing. This development is driven by changes in lifestyle patterns and increasing community needs, especially in big cities (Indrawan et al., 2021). This is in line with changes in the level of per capita income which are rising and growing, so that opportunities for lifestyle changes are also changing. According to (Kerr, 2017)), this community lifestyle is claimed to make the culinary business increasingly promising. Apart from that, this behavior arises because of the rapid development of technology which creates opportunities for the domestic culinary industry to develop, especially regional culinary products. The emergence of various culinary places such as cafes, shops and coffee shops in the area shows that the food and beverage business is accepted by the people in that location. Consumers who choose cafes as a place to eat not only show the quality of the food but also the appropriate quality of service. Therefore, managers must provide the right quality of service and product quality in order to compete with other cafes, shops or coffeeshops. To be able to survive amidst the growing competition for cafes in an area, it encourages owners to create appropriate marketing strategies, of course consumer-oriented marketing strategies (Mahastra, 2017).

Product quality is closely related to the product's ability to perform its function, including the overall product, reliability, accuracy, ease of operation and repair, other valuable attributes. So product quality is a set of characteristics and characteristics of goods and services that have the ability to meet needs, is a combined meaning of reliability, accuracy, convenience, maintenance and other attributes of a product. According to (Asti & Ayuningtyas, 2020) Product quality is the product's ability to perform its function, this includes the useful life of the product, reliability, ease, use and repair, and other values. Product quality can be viewed from two points of view, namely an internal point of view and an external point of view. Another factor that can influence consumer satisfaction is service quality, namely efforts to fulfill consumer needs and desires and the consistency of delivery in keeping with consumer expectations. Service quality based on previous researchers' findings provides evidence that there is a significant influence between service quality and consumer satisfaction (Bahar & Sjahrudin, 2015). Service quality, apart from having an influence on consumer satisfaction, also has an influence on purchasing interest. This is shown by research (Zakaria & Sri, 2013) that service quality has a positive and significant effect on consumer buying interest. Good service can determine consumer satisfaction, including service quality such as physical evidence (palpable), reliability (trustability), responsiveness (responsiveness), guarantee (assurance) and empathy (Kerr, 2017).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Product Quality

Product quality is the ability of a product to carry out its function, this includes overall continuity, reliability, deliciousness, ease of operation and product form and other product attributes (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Quality

reflects all the benefits of product sacrifices that produce benefits for consumers. Product quality is a specificity of a product or service that depends on its ability to meet stated or inferred consumer requirements (Kotler & Keller, 2012). Indicators in measuring product quality include;

- a. entertainment;
- b. continuity (existence);
- c. characteristics;
- d. trustworthy(trustworthy);
- e. aesthetic(aesthetic);
- f. conformity to specifications (conformity to specifications);
- g. perceived quality (print of quality).

Service Quality

Service quality is all forms of service provision provided optimally by the company to meet client needs in accordance with customer expectations (Tjiptono, 2014). Quality is also defined as an economic activity effort that produces time, place, form or distance traveled or psychological usefulness (Juhana & Mulyawan, 2015). Service quality indicators according to (Kotler & Armstrong, 2012) videlicet;

- a. trustworthy;
- b. responsiveness;
- c. belief;
- d. empathy;
- e. Palpable.

Consumer Satisfaction

Consumer satisfaction is the position where the perceived product performance is in line with the buyer's expectations, but on the other hand consumers will also be disappointed if the product performance does not meet expectations (Wijaya & Hidayati, 2021). Meanwhile, according to (Sihite et al., 2018) consumer satisfaction is a measure of the success of marketing strategies in marketing products. Measuring customer satisfaction is not an easy job and requires certain criteria. Based on the description of consumer satisfaction, it can be interpreted that consumer satisfaction is the perceived position of product performance in accordance with buyer expectations. Increasing consumer satisfaction has the possibility of long-term and short-term growth which has an impact on repeat purchases. The consumer satisfaction indicators developed (Bhinawan & Ali, 2017) are; a) Anticipation; b) Experience; c) Overall satisfaction; d) Recommend other products; e) Showing impunity towards competitors' offers.

Purchasing Decision

A decision is the selection of two or more purchasing options that are very necessary, meaning that for someone to make a decision, several choices that are very necessary must be available. Purchasing decisions can determine how the decision-making process is carried out (Mihart, 2012). This is in line

with the opinion of (Wardhani et al., 2016) which explains that a purchasing decision is a decision as a choice of action from two or more very necessary options. Meanwhile (Kotler et al., 2006) explains that the purchasing decision is a decision process consisting of five stages carried out by a consumer before arriving at a purchasing decision and also post-purchase. Purchasing decision indicators are; a) product introduction; b) information hunting; c) evaluation is very necessary; d) purchase decision; e) buyer behavior.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework of Research

METHODS

This type of research is quantitative descriptive research with primary data collected through research instruments in the form of questionnaires distributed to respondents via online Google Form. The population in this study was 540 people taken from visitor data over a period of 3 months, namely purchase data from June 2023 to August 2023, where visitors who attended were categorized as regular buyers and some were incidental or not regular visitors. The sample was determined using the purposive sampling method (Sugiyono, 2018) using the Slovin formula, with the following numbers :

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + (Ne^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{540}{1+(540*0,05^2)} \quad n = \frac{540}{1+(540*0,0025)} \quad n = \frac{540}{1+1,35} \quad n = \frac{540}{2,35} \quad n = 276,9 \text{ or } 277 \text{ Customer}$$

Data analysis was carried out using the Partial Least Square (PLS) method using SmartPLS version 3 software. Hypothesis testing used full model structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis with SmartPLS. In the full model structural equation modeling, apart from confirming the theory, it also explains whether or not there is a relationship between latent variables (Ghozali & Nasehudin, 2012) Hypothesis testing is by looking at the calculated value of the Path Coefficient in inner model testing.

RESULTS

Description of Research Objects

The description of the answers based on male gender has a probability value of 0.58 or 58% with a total of 160 people, and female gender has a value of 0.42 or 42% with a total of 117 people. This shows that there are more male consumers at Bang Pendi Cafe than female consumers. Description of answers

based on age, aged 15-25 years has a percentage value of 0.51 or 51% as many as 142 people, and aged 26-35 years is 0.23 or 23% or as many as 63 people, aged 36-45 years is 0, 19 or 19% or 54 people, the remaining 6% are over 45 years old. This shows that consumers aged 15-25 years at the Bang Pendi Cafe dominate because this age is considered young and teenagers so they prefer to hang out at the cafe. The description of answers based on occupation shows that consumers who are still students have an opportunity value of 0.35 or 35% with a total of 98 people and entrepreneurs of 0.20 or 20% with a total of 55 people, employees of 0.12 or 12% or as many as 32 people, and government employees amounting to 0.6 or 6% or as many as 18 people, the remaining 27% or 78 people are casual workers and do not settle. This shows that based on occupation/profession, consumers with professions who are still in school or students are the most dominant consumers at Bang Pendi Cafe.

PLS (Partial Least Square) Analysis

In this research, product quality and service quality on satisfaction and purchasing decisions will be analyzed using smartPLS analysis. The stages in PLS analysis include the measurement model testing stage (Outer Model) and the structural model testing stage (Inner Model).

Figure 2 Construct Validity Test

Source: SmartPLS Data Processing (2023)

Evaluation of Model Measurements (Outer Model)

The measurement model testing stage includes testing Convergent Validity, Discriminant Validity and Composite Reliability. The results of PLS analysis can be used to test research hypotheses if all indicators in the PLS model meet the requirements for convergent validity, discriminant validity and composite reliability.

Convergent Validity (Convergent Validity)

The convergent validity test is carried out by looking at the loading factor value of each indicator on the construct. An indicator is said to have good reliability if the outer loading value is above 0.70, (Sarwono, 2014). So the

loading factor limit used to test the convergent validity of each indicator is 0.70. The following is the explanation.

Table 1 Validity of Variable Instruments

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	Rule of Thumb	Conclusion
Product Quality (X_1)	X1.1	0.988	0.700	Valid
	X1.2	0.977	0.700	Valid
	X1.3	0.980	0.700	Valid
	X1.4	0.975	0.700	Valid
	X1.5	0.976	0.700	Valid
Quality of Service (X_2)	X2.1	0.898	0.700	Valid
	X2.2	0.949	0.700	Valid
	X2.3	0.955	0.700	Valid
	X2.4	0.938	0.700	Valid
	X2.5	0.779	0.700	Valid
Consumer Satisfaction (Y)	Y1.1	0.925	0.700	Valid
	Y1.2	0.930	0.700	Valid
	Y1.3	0.905	0.700	Valid
	Y1.4	0.930	0.700	Valid
	Y1.5	0.917	0.700	Valid
Buying Decision (Z)	Z.1	0.955	0.700	Valid
	Z.2	0.961	0.700	Valid
	Z.3	0.973	0.700	Valid
	Z.4	0.979	0.700	Valid

Source: SmartPLS 2023 Data Processing

Based on the table above, it is stated that the results of the instrument validity test for each variable have a valid loading factor value or meet the requirements. Apart from looking at the factor loading value of each indicator, the convergent validity test was also carried out by looking at the AVE value of each construct. The model was declared to have met the required convergent validity if each construct had an AVE value above 0.5.

Table 2 AVE Value

Variabels	AVE Value
Product Quality (X_1)	0.849
Kualitas Pelayanan (X_2)	0.935
Consumer Satisfaction (Y)	0.821
Buying Decision (Z)	0.959

The results of the analysis in the table above show that the constructs of promotional strategy, service quality and price, and purchasing decisions mean that each construct has met good convergent validity.

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity assessment has come generally accepted prerequisite for assaying connections between idle variables. For friction-grounded structural equation modeling, similar as partial least places, the Fornell- Larcker criterion and cross-loading checks are the dominant approaches to assessing discriminant validity. Discriminant validity is the position of isolation of an index in measuring the instrument construct. To test discriminant validity, it can be done by examining Cross Loading, videlicet the correlation measure of an index with its associated construct(cross lading) compared with the correlation measure with another construct(cross lading). The value of the index correlation construct must be lesser for the associated construct than for other constructs. A larger value indicates the felicity of an index to explain the associated construct compared to explaining other constructs (Henseler et al., 2014).

Table 2 Discriminant Validity

Items	Satisfaction (Y)	Purchase Decision (Z)	Service Quality (X ₂)	Product Quality (X ₁)
X1-1	0.853	0.005	0.141	0.988
X1-2	0.866	0.063	0.126	0.977
X1-3	0.861	0.021	0.141	0.980
X1-4	0.833	0.058	0.112	0.975
X1-5	0.848	0.005	0.130	0.976
X2-1	0.177	-0.014	0.898	0.117
X2-2	0.182	-0.045	0.949	0.114
X2-3	0.184	-0.051	0.955	0.127
X2-4	0.189	-0.067	0.938	0.157
X2-5	0.094	-0.093	0.779	0.070
Y1.1	0.925	0.066	0.135	0.763
Y1.2	0.930	0.131	0.177	0.712
Y1.3	0.905	0.045	0.148	0.966
Y1.4	0.930	0.073	0.184	0.760
Y1.5	0.917	0.107	0.224	0.758
Z.1	0.051	0.955	-0.043	0.006
Z.2	0.091	0.961	-0.038	0.033
Z.3	0.096	0.973	-0.064	0.026
Z.4	0.096	0.979	-0.070	0.049

Source: Smartpls Data Processing 2023

Based on the table above is the cross loading value of each construct or variable for each indicator.

Table 3 Fornell-Larcker Criterion Discriminant Validity

	Satisfaction (Y)	Purchase Decision (Z)	Service Quality (X₂)	Product Quality (X₁)
Satisfaction (Y)	0.921			
Purchase Decision (Z)	0.089	0.967		
Service Quality (X ₂)	0.187	-0.057	0.906	
Product Quality (X ₁)	0.870	0.031	0.133	0.979

Source: PLS 2023 Data Processing

From the results of the table above, it shows that the discriminant validity value of each indicator item for the construct is greater than the cross loading value. Thus, it can be concluded that all constructs or latent variables have good discriminant validity, where in the block the construct indicators are better than the other block indicators.

Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha

After testing the validity of the construct, the next test is the construct reliability test which is measured by Composite Reliability (CR) from the indicator block that measures the CR construct which is used to display good reliability. A construct is declared reliable if the composite reliability value is > 0.6. According to Hair et al. (2014) the composite reliability coefficient must be greater than 0.7 although a value of 0.6 is still acceptable. However, internal consistency testing is not absolutely necessary if construct validity has been met, because a valid construct is a reliable one, whereas a reliable construct is not necessarily valid (Blumberg et al., 2014).

Table 4 Construct Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Satisfaction (Y)	0.956	0.966
Purchase Decision (Z)	0.977	0.983
Service Quality (X ₂)	0.945	0.958
Product Quality (X ₁)	0.989	0.991

Source: Smartpls Data Processing 2023

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the results of the Cronbach's Alpha and composite reliability tests show a value of > 0.6, which means that all constructs are declared reliable.

Structural Model Testing (Inner Model)

After evaluating the model and finding that each construct meets the requirements for Convergent Validity, Discriminant Validity and Composite Reliability, the next step is to evaluate the structural model which includes testing model fit, Path Coefficient and R². Model fit testing is used to find out whether a model fits the data.

- a. Path Coeffisient

Table 5 Path Coefesient

Variabel	Path Coefesient	Persentase
X1 -> Y1	0,329	32,9%
X1 -> Z	0,307	30,7%
X2 -> Y1	0,179	17,9%
X2 -> Z	0,225	22,5%
Y -> Y1	0,447	44,7%

Source: Smartpls Data Processing 2023

Based on the image which is the result of eliminating several invalid statements, the Product Quality variable has an influence on the Consumer Satisfaction variable of 0.329 or 32,9%. The Product Quality variable has an influence on the Purchasing Decision variable by 0.307 or 30.7%. The Service Quality variable has an influence on the Consumer Satisfaction variable of 0,179 or 17,9%. The Service Quality variable has an influence on the Purchasing Decision variable by 0,225 or 22,5%. The Consumer Satisfaction variable has an influence on the Purchasing Decision variable of 0,447 or 44,7%.

b. Fit Models

Mod Based on the results of the tests carried out, the following results/outputs were obtained: el Fit :

Table 6 Saturated Model

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
NFI	0.815	0.815

Source: smartpls data processing 2023

NFI values ranging from 0 – 1 are derived from a comparison between the hypothesized model and a certain independent model. The model has a high fit if the value is close to 1. Based on the table above, the NFI value is 0.815, which means the model has a good fit (Ghozali & Nasehudin, 2012)

c. R Square

Inner models (inner relations, structural models, and substantive theory) describe the relationship between latent variables based on substantive theory. The structural model is evaluated using R-square for the dependent construct. The R² value can be used to assess the influence of certain endogenous variables and whether exogenous variables have a substantive influence (Ghozali, 2012). R² results of 0.67, 0.33, and 0.19 indicate that the model is "good", "moderate", and "weak" .

Table 7 R Square

Variabel	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Satisfaction (Y)	0.763	0.761
Purchase Decision (Z)	0.023	0.013

Source: Smartpls data processing 2023

Based on the table above, it is found that the satisfaction variable has an R Square value of 0.763, this means that 76.3% of the variation or change in consumer satisfaction and consumer purchasing decisions is influenced by

product quality and service quality, while the purchasing decision variable has a value of 0.022 which means 0.2 % while the remaining 37.7% was explained by other causes. So it can be said that the R Square on the variable consumer satisfaction and consumer purchasing decisions is moderate.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is calculated based on direct influence, which can be seen in the following picture:

Figure 2 SmartPLS 2023 Hypothesis Test
Source: Data processed by SEM PLS 2023

To find out the structural relationship between latent variables, hypothesis testing must be carried out on the path coefficient between variables by comparing the p-value with alpha (0.005) or a t-statistic of (>1.96). The P-value and t-statistics are obtained from the output in SmartPLS using the bootstrapping method.

Table 7 Hypothesis Testing

	T Statistik	P Values
Product Quality (X ₁) -> Satisfaction (Y)	3.404	0.000
Service Quality (X ₂) -> Customer Satisfaction (Y)	2.397	0.017
Product Quality (X ₁) -> Purchase Decision (Z)	1.559	0.120
Service Quality (X ₂) -> Purchase Decision (Z)	1.192	0.234
Consumer Satisfaction (Y) -> Purchase Decision (Z)	2.098	0.036

Source: SmartPLS Data Processing 2023

Based on the table above, it can be seen the significance of the influence of each variable on product quality, service quality, satisfaction and purchasing decisions, with the following explanation:

Hypothesis Test 1:

Ho1: There is no influence of Product Quality on Consumer Satisfaction.

Ha1: There is an influence of product quality on consumer satisfaction.

Based on table 4.12 with a P-Value value of $0.000 < 0.05$ or with a t-statistic of $3.404 > 1.96$, then H_01 is rejected and H_{a1} is accepted, which means that product quality influences consumer satisfaction.

Hypothesis Test 2:

H_02 : There is no influence of Service Quality on Consumer Satisfaction.

H_{a2} : There is an influence of Service Quality on Consumer Satisfaction.

Based on table 4.12 with a P-Value value of $0.017 < 0.05$ or with a t-statistic of $2.397 > 1.96$, H_02 is rejected and H_{a2} is accepted, which means that Service Quality influences Consumer Satisfaction.

Hypothesis Test 3:

H_03 : There is no influence of product quality on purchasing decisions.

H_{a3} : There is an influence of product quality on purchasing decisions.

Based on table 4.12 with a P-Value value of $0.120 > 0.05$ or with a t-statistic of $1.559 < 1.96$, H_03 is accepted and H_{a3} is rejected, which means that Product Quality has no significant effect. on Purchasing Decisions.

Hypothesis Test 4:

H_04 : There is no influence of Service Quality on Purchasing Decisions.

H_{a4} : There is an influence of Service Quality on Purchasing Decisions.

Based on table 4.12 with a P-Value value of $0.234 > 0.05$ or with a T-statistic of $1.192 < 1.96$, H_04 is accepted and H_{a4} is rejected, which means that Service Quality has no significant effect. on Purchasing Decisions.

Hypothesis Test 5:

H_05 : There is no influence of Consumer Satisfaction (Y) on Purchasing Decisions (Z).

H_{a5} : There is an influence of product quality on consumer satisfaction.

Based on table 4.12 above with a PV value of $0.036 < 0.05$ or with a T count of $2.098 > 1.96$, H_05 is rejected and H_{a5} is accepted, which means that Consumer Satisfaction has a sig. on Purchasing Decisions

DISCUSSION

This research discusses the influence of product and service quality on consumer satisfaction and purchasing decisions (Study at the Bang Pendi Rantauprapat Cafe).

Product Quality on Consumer Satisfaction

The research results show that product quality has a significant effect on consumer satisfaction. This is proven by looking at the t test results which show the value of 3,404 is greater than the t table value of 1.96 and the sig value of $0.000 < 0.05$ with a percentage of 34.0%. This means that if product quality is improved, customer satisfaction will increase, and vice versa. Therefore, product quality is something that Bang Pendi Cafe needs to pay attention to. This is in line with the research carried out (Jordi & Prabantoro, 2021) which also concluded that product quality influences consumer satisfaction. The

results of this research are also in accordance with research conducted by (Ibrahim & Thawil, 2019) and (Fadhli & Pratiwi, 2021) which shows that product quality has a significant effect on customer satisfaction.

Service Quality on Consumer Satisfaction

The results of the research show that there is a positive and significant influence of the service quality variable on consumer satisfaction at Bang Pendi Cafe. This is proven by looking at the results of the t test which has been carried out showing a t value of 2.397 which is greater than the t table value of 1.96 and a sig value of $0.017 < 0.05$ with a percentage of 23.9%, meaning that if service quality is improved then customer satisfaction will increase, and vice versa. Therefore, service quality is something that Bang Pendi Cafe needs to pay attention to. The results of this research are in accordance with research conducted by (Ibrahim & Thawil, 2019) and (Mentang et al., 2021) which suggests that there is an influence of service quality on customer satisfaction.

Product Quality on Purchasing Decisions

The research results show that the product quality variable has no significant effect on purchasing decisions. This is proven by looking at the results of the t test that has been carried out, which shows a value of 1.559 which is smaller than the tolerance error value of 1.96 with a sig value amounting to $0.120 > 0.05$ with a percentage of 15.5%. This is in line with the research conducted (Lubis, 2021) and (Kurnianingsih & Sugiyanto, 2021) which concludes that product quality is not the main thing that drives consumers to make purchasing decisions. Consumers at the Bang Pendi Cafe enjoy food and drinks, perhaps due to other factors that influence their purchasing decisions.

Service Quality on Purchasing Decisions

The research results show that the service quality variable has no influence on the purchasing decision variable. This is proven by looking at the test results that have been carried out showing a value of 1.192 which is smaller than the tolerance error value of $t = 1.96$ with a value of sig. $0.234 > 0.05$ with a percentage of 11.9%. The results of this research are also in accordance with research conducted by (Haryanto, 2013) who also found that service quality did not have a positive effect on purchasing decisions. Further research was carried out (Faroh, 2017) which also proves that service has a strong influence on purchasing decisions. From these results, it can be concluded that service quality is not the dominant factor that drives purchasing decisions at Bang Pendi Cafe.

Consumer Satisfaction with Purchasing Decisions

The research results show that consumer satisfaction has a significant effect on purchasing decision variables. This is proven by looking at the test results that have been carried out showing a value of 2,098 which is greater than the tolerance error value of $t = 1.96$ with a value of sig. $0.036 > 0.05$ with a percentage of 20.9%. The results of this research are also in accordance with the results of research conducted by (Hidayat, 2015) and (Halim & Syamsuri, 2016) which shows that service quality has a positive effect on consumer satisfaction.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the discussions that have been carried out, the conclusions of this research are as follows:

1. Product quality (X1) has a partially positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction (Y). These results can be seen by looking at the results of the inner model test, where the statistical t value is greater than the t table value, namely $6.591 > 1.96$ with a percentage value of 65.9%. So it can be concluded that H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted or proven.
2. Service quality (X2) has a partially positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction (Y). These results can be seen by looking at the results of the inner model test, where the statistical t value is greater than the t table value, namely $2.603 > 1.96$ with a percentage value of 26.0%. So it can be concluded that H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted or proven.
3. Product quality (X1) has a partially positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions (Z). These results can be seen by looking at the results of the inner model test, where the statistical t value is greater than the t table value, namely $6.377 > 1.96$ with a percentage value of 63.7%. So it can be concluded that H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted or proven.
4. Service quality (X2) has a partially positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions (Z). These results can be seen by looking at the results of the inner model test, where the statistical t value is greater than the t table value, namely $5.168 > 1.96$ with a percentage value of 51.6%. So it can be concluded that H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted or proven.
5. Product quality (X1) and service quality (X2) simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions (Z) through consumer satisfaction (Y). These results can be seen by looking at the results of the inner model test, where the statistical t value is greater than the t table value, namely $8.636 > 1.96$ with a percentage value of 86.3%. So it can be concluded that H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted or prove.

FURTHER STUDY

This research is quantitative descriptive in nature, where data collection uses a questionnaire instrument that is distributed online, so there is concern that there will be high deviations in answers. For this reason, it is hoped that future researchers will further enrich research methods and varied data collection and analysis techniques.

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